

Does the difference make a difference? Evaluating Contracts for Difference design in a fully decarbonised European electricity market

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ABSTRACT

The future electricity market is subject to several uncertainties, which expose both investors and consumers to significant price risks. Contracts for Difference (CfDs) between the government and generators of renewable electricity can mitigate these risks, as they stipulate payments determined by the difference of a reference market price and a strike price. Therefore, they gained popularity amidst high electricity prices during the energy crisis in 2022. Depending on their specific design, CfDs can distort investment and dispatch decisions. We compare two two-sided volume-based CfDs with different reference prices, a volume-based one-sided CfD and the newly proposed financial CfD in a sector-coupled European electricity market in absence of carbon-emitting technologies. Implementing the CfDs for two wind onshore technologies by bidding zone in an optimisation model, we find that investments and dispatch incentives set by CfD design impact the utilization of wind capacities, particularly by electrolysers. Accordingly, system costs are lowest under the financial CfD, which was designed to remove distortions of volume-based CfDs. However, it also experiences the highest uncertainty of ex post cost-recovery for investors. We conclude that an adequate risk premium could address this issue and should be subject to future research.

1. Introduction

Early support schemes for variable renewables (vREs), namely, wind and solar power, were designed to promote investments in a new and yet costly technology. In Europe, the majority of primarily implemented instruments were price-based mechanisms, such as fixed feed-in tariffs, that assure cost recovery at low risk (Kitzing et al., 2012; del Río and Mir-Artigues, 2014; Barnea et al., 2022). This policy successfully established vREs as important source of electricity (Bolkesjø et al., 2014). Despite declining technology costs (IRENA, 2018), vREs in today's markets continue to require governmental support as the increasing market shares of renewables decreases electricity prices (merit-order effect) and own market values (cannibalization effect) (Hirth, 2013; Sensfuß et al., 2008; Gelabert et al., 2011; Burgos-Payán et al., 2013; López Prola et al., 2020). As technologies evolve, Kitzing et al. (2020) suggest to move from a price-setting to a quantity-setting policy through auctions. Indeed, the administratively determined remuneration rates of early support schemes in, e.g., Germany, Spain and Denmark, experienced rising support costs typically carried by consumers (Green and Yatchew, 2012). With the aim to decrease these costs, the European Renewable Energy

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Directive (RED) as of 2018 prescribes to award support schemes within competitive tendering procedures (Directive 2018/2001). The RED further requires renewable support schemes to be designed in a manner that maximizes their market integration, namely, to expose them to market prices and set the incentive to maximize market revenues (Directive 2018/2001). With this policy, the European Union is in line with the global support scheme landscape being increasingly dominated by market-based instruments (Barnea et al., 2022).

It is widely accepted that vREs will constitute the dominant source of power in a fully decarbonised European energy system. Scenario results for vRE shares of future European power generation range from at least 40% (Zappa et al., 2019) to 75%–78% (Child et al., 2019). *Ceteris paribus*, this exacerbates the merit-order and cannibalization effect, perpetuating vRE's dependence on support schemes. However, resulting price decreases could be smaller than generally believed if the remaining capacity mix adjusted to high vRE shares (Green and Vasilakos, 2011; Helistö et al., 2017). On the path to decarbonization, CO₂-prices will play an important role in stabilizing market values of vREs (Brown and Reichenberg, 2021; Liebensteiner and Naumann, 2022; Finke et al., 2023). In absence of CO₂-prices, flexible demand in sectors coupled with the power system could be able to set market prices above vREs' low marginal costs, when deployed optimally (Lynch et al., 2019; Roach and Meeus, 2020; Bernath et al., 2021; Härtel and Korpås, 2021; Ruhnu, 2022; Böttger and Härtel, 2022; Mallapragada et al., 2023). Thus, future electricity prices are subject to several uncertainties, such as the deployment of flexible heating systems or electrolyzers. A power system dominated by capital-intensive investments requires renewable support instruments capable of addressing corresponding price risks (Beiter et al., 2023). Contracts for Difference (CfDs) constitute such an instrument. They stipulate payments between the government and generators of renewable electricity defined by the difference of an *ex post* realized reference market price and an *ex ante* agreed-upon strike price (Beiter et al., 2023; Schlecht et al., 2024). The same mechanism can also be referred to as sliding or variable market premium (Huntington et al., 2017). Alike sliding market premia, CfDs can be one-sided, if they only require payments to the renewable electricity producer when the strike price is below the reference price, or two-sided, if they also enable governments to collect payments otherwise. Since governmental revenues from CfDs can be transferred to consumers, two-sided CfDs also allow to hedge consumers from high energy prices. Therefore, they gained popularity among policy-makers under the impression of extremely high electricity prices during the energy crisis in 2022 (European Commission, 2022). Alongside other measures, the European Commission proposed to amend European electricity market design regulations with the obligation to design support schemes for renewables as two-sided CfDs (European Commission, 2023).

While the allowed direction of payments under a CfD affects the allocation of risks between consumers and investors, other design elements may influence market dynamics. Particularly, a CfD's underlying reference price crucially determines the incentives for the investment and dispatch decision of contracted electricity generators. For the most simple type of CfD, it is equal to the hourly spot market price, eliminating the asset owner's exposure to

spot market prices. Effectively, it is equivalent to a feed-in tariff, which sets the incentive to maximize electricity output in both the investment and operational phase. Yet, from a system perspective it may be more beneficial to foster investments in renewables that achieve high market values rather than output (Ueckerdt et al., 2013). Therefore, CfD payments are often decoupled from individual market revenues by defining the reference price as an average market value or price over a certain period. However, expected revenues or costs associated with anticipated payments per electricity sold virtually increase or decrease variable costs with consequences for short-term operational efficiency. Detailed conceptual discussion of these effects are provided by Schlecht et al. (2024), Newbery (2023) and Huntington et al. (2017) who congruently propose to decouple support payments from own market revenues on the one hand and produced volume on the other.

Due to the predicted future prevalence of CfDs for renewables, it is crucial to study the implications of their different design options on the future electricity market (Beiter et al., 2023). Applying wind investment models, the impact of subsidy design on location choice was studied by Schmidt et al. (2013), on technology choice by May (2017) and on both by Meus et al. (2021). An assessment based on historical German data is provided by Grothe and Müsgens (2013). All studies conclude that fixed market premia support schemes that expose generators to market prices, favor investments in more system-friendly wind power plants with higher market values. Hitaj and Löschel (2019) empirically estimate that support schemes rewarding different locations are indeed more cost-effective in reducing greenhouse gas emissions. Yet, these analyses neglect indications of support scheme design for market prices and dispatch. In a theoretical model, Andor and Voss (2016) show how fixed feed-in tariff cause welfare losses as they set the incentive to generate electricity, even if technical operational costs are above electricity prices. Consequently, they can cause negative electricity prices. De Vos (2015) and Frondel et al. (2022) provide empirical evidence for the relationship of feed-in tariffs and negative prices in German spot markets. In an agent-based dispatch model, Frey et al. (2020) simulate how renewable bidding strategies under market premia cause negative market prices up to the negative level of the premium. Implications on operational efficiency were modelled by Chaves-Avila et al. (2017) and Rosnes (2014) who find that shielding renewables from market price signals decreases their flexibility. Due to increasing thermal costs optimal operation is only achieved by a capacity-based premium. However, negative prices resulting from market premia can reduce curtailment, such that a target share of renewable electricity generation can be achieved more cost-effectively (Pahle et al., 2016). This result is in line with Özdemir et al. (2020) whose analysis covers future scenarios of the whole European power system. Fais et al. (2014) additionally consider feedback of support schemes on consumer levies in Germany, while Simshauser (2019) assesses the impact of increasing shares of ‘out-of-market’ renewables on the forward market in Australia. Further work focuses on the implications of different support schemes in terms of risk. Neuhoff et al. (2022) analytically show that financing costs increase with a higher dependence on uncertain market revenues. Breitschopf and Alexander-Haw (2022) estimate that support schemes capable of lowering market price

risks decrease projects' WACCs. Devine et al. (2017) stress the relevance of risk preferences for support scheme design choices.

To the best of our knowledge, this paper constitutes the first attempt to study vRE support schemes in a scenario of a future European electricity market in absence of carbon pricing and with a high level of sector-coupling. We evaluate four different types of Contracts for Difference (CfDs) that are issued to two distinct wind onshore technologies by bidding zone: two two-sided CfDs with volume-based payments based on different reference prices, a volume-based one-sided CfD and the newly proposed financial CfD, which we interpret to be capacity-based. In a brownfield optimisation model, we simulate a target scenario of a fully decarbonised, sector-coupled European power system with a high share of non-thermal electricity generation. Assuming that the target scenario results represent investors' expectations on market outcomes, we derive optimal strike prices that would result in a competitive auction for each type of CfDs considered. Subsequently, we simulate four CfD scenarios by manipulating our model's wind onshore investment and/or variable costs according to corresponding expected CfD payments. The main contribution of our work is three-fold: First, from a system perspective, our approach enables us to analyze how investment and dispatch incentives set by different types of CfDs affect the overall energy system in terms of market prices, curtailment and electrolyser deployment. Second, from investors' perspective, we illustrate how ex ante expectations on CfD payments deviate from their ex post realizations. Third, from consumers' perspective, we evaluate how different types of CfDs perform in terms of total system costs including CfD expenditures. The optimisation is carried out using the Backbone energy system modelling tool (Helistö et al., 2019).

The remainder of the paper is organized as follows: Section 2 provides a formal definition of CfDs studied in this paper. Section 3 lays out our methodology for the target and CfD scenario simulations. Section 4 presents and discusses results, while Section 5 concludes and derives policy implications.

2. Theoretical background

Contracts for Difference (CfDs) for renewable electricity are financial contracts between the government and generators of renewable electricity. They specify payments from the government to the electricity generator if a reference market price for electricity is below an agreed-upon strike price and can include a reverse payment otherwise (Schlecht et al., 2024). There exist different types of CfDs that differ in terms of the definition of these payments. We define annual profits $\Pi_{i,n}$ of a power plant of technology $i \in \{1, 2, \dots, I\}$ in bidding zone $n \in N$ under a CfD to be given by

$$\Pi_{i,n} = \sum_{t=1}^T (q_{t,i,n} p_{t,n}) - C_{i,n} + P_{i,n}^{\text{type}}, \quad (1)$$

where the first term in Equation (1) represents the power plant's annual wholesale market revenues. Particularly, $q_{t,i,n}$ denotes power sold by power plant i in hour $t \in \{1, 2, \dots, T\}$ with $T = 8760$ for price $p_{t,n}$ in bidding zone n 's wholesale electricity market. A power plant's annual costs, $C_{i,n}$, are composed by operating costs with variable costs c and investment costs M per installed capacity $Q_{i,n}$. They are annualized with annuity factor A , such that $C_{i,n} = \sum_{t=1}^T cq_{t,i,n} + AMQ_{i,n}$ with uniform c , A and M over all power plants and bidding zones. $P_{i,n}^{\text{type}}$ denote annual net payments from the government (negative if to the government). They are defined by type of CfD, of which we consider four, as denoted by the superscript type $\in \{\text{basic}, 1\text{way}, 2\text{way}, \text{fin}\}$. We assume the contracts' durations to be equal to the power plant's economic lifetime.

Payments are generally defined by the difference of a power-plant-individual strike price, $S_{i,n}^{\text{type}}$ and a reference market price, $p_n^{\text{R,type}}$, which is uniform in each bidding zone n . The reference market price is determined ex post, whereas the strike price is agreed upon ex ante. We consider three volume-based CfDs, whose payments are made by electricity sold in the wholesale market. We denominate *basic* CfD, if the reference price is equal to the hourly market price, i.e., $p_n^{\text{R,basic}} = p_{t,n}$, such that payments are given by

$$P_{i,n}^{\text{basic}} = \sum_{t=1}^T q_{t,i,n} (S_{i,n}^{\text{basic}} - p_{t,n}). \quad (2)$$

Conversely, reference prices of the volume-based *1way* and *2way* CfD are determined by the annual average of generation-weighted market revenues, namely the market value v_n , of all new wind onshore power plants in bidding zone n , i.e.,

$$p_n^{\text{R,1way}} = p_n^{\text{R,2way}} = v_n \equiv \frac{\sum_{t=1}^T \sum_{i=1}^I q_{t,i,n} p_{t,n}}{\sum_{t=1}^T \sum_{i=1}^I q_{t,i,n}}. \quad (3)$$

We refer to a CfD with this reference price as *2way* CfD, if it allows for both positive and negative net payments given by

$$P_{i,n}^{\text{2way}} = \sum_{t=1}^T q_{t,i,n} (S_{i,n}^{\text{2way}} - v_n). \quad (4)$$

We call it *1way* CfD, if only positive net payments are allowed:

$$P_{i,n}^{\text{1way}} = \sum_{t=1}^T q_{t,i,n} \max \{0, S_{i,n}^{\text{1way}} - v_n\}. \quad (5)$$

Finally, we consider the so-called *financial* CfD as proposed by Schlecht et al. (2024), where net payments are independent of a power plant's electricity generation. In particular, the authors propose power plants to receive a fixed

hourly payment, $S_{i,n}^{\text{fin}}$, from the government in exchange for paying the revenues of a reference power plant, r_n . Amongst other options, these can be defined by total market revenues in a bidding zone normalized by installed capacity, i.e.,

$$r_n = \frac{\sum_{t=1}^T \sum_{i=1}^I q_{t,i,n} p_{t,n}}{\sum_{i=1}^I Q_{i,n}}. \quad (6)$$

Accordingly, we define the strike price to refer to installed capacity instead of volume of electricity generation, such that payment are given by

$$P_{i,n}^{\text{fin}} = Q_{i,n}(S_{i,n}^{\text{fin}} - r_n^{\text{fin}}). \quad (7)$$

This interpretation of the *financial* CfD resembles the capacity-based support scheme proposed by Huntington et al. (2017), where subsidy payments are calculated based on a reference plant's profitability gap using both its costs and market revenues. In contrast, the *financial* CfD considers the power plant's own costs for the calculation of the strike price¹.

According to European law, renewable support schemes must be awarded within a 'competitive tendering procedure' (Directive 2018/2001). As in Neuhoff et al. (2022), we consider CfDs to be awarded to a target level of new wind onshore capacity within zonal pay-as-bid auctions for the CfDs' underlying strike price. This resembles the procedure implemented for sliding market premia for renewable projects in Germany as of 2017 (Anatolitis and Welisch, 2017). In a perfectly competitive auction, a rational, risk-neutral investor chooses a strike price that sets expected profits over lifetime to zero. We derive optimal strike prices $S_{i,n}^{\text{type}}$ for all type $\in \{\text{basic}, \text{1way}, \text{2way}, \text{fin}\}$ assuming that all future hourly prices $p_{t,n}$, and power sales, $q_{t,i,n}$ are known to the investor and the same over $t \in \{1, 2, \dots, T\}$ in each year of $D > 0$ years of economic lifetime. For the *basic* CfD, this implies to choose $S_{i,n}^{\text{basic}}$, such that

$$D \cdot \Pi_{i,n} = D \cdot \sum_{t=1}^T \left(q_{t,i,n} p_{t,n} + q_{t,i,n} (S_{i,n}^{\text{basic}} - p_{t,n}) \right) - D \cdot C_{i,n} = 0 \iff S_{i,n}^{\text{basic}} = \frac{C_{i,n}}{\sum_{t=1}^T q_{t,i,n}} \equiv \text{lcoe}_{i,n} \quad (8)$$

with $\sum_{t=1}^T q_{t,i,n}$ being strictly positive. Hence, in theory, it is optimal to bid a strike price equal to power-plant-specific levelized cost of electricity (LCOE), which we define according to Kost et al. (2021). Consequently, *basic* CfDs are awarded to power plants with the lowest LCOE. Under our assumption of equal investment and operating costs, wind power plants incurring low LCOE are characterized by a high number of full load hours. However, from a welfare perspective, it can be desirable for investors to also take into account power plants' expected market values as an

¹Note that our definitions do not limit CfD payments to positive wholesale market prices. Market-based curtailment is assumed not to be remunerated, while curtailment due to grid-congestion is neglected.

indication of their value for the system. For instance, power plants whose electricity generation is lower in total, but more correlated with residual load could reduce the need for costly flexible supply or demand capacities (Ueckerdt et al., 2013). Prices resulting from a functioning wholesale market usually incentivise such system-friendly investments (Grothe and Müsgens, 2013; Schmidt et al., 2013; May, 2017; Meus et al., 2021). By design, the *basic* CfD entirely eliminates exposure to market prices.

On these grounds, investors are able to keep their above-average market revenues under our *1way* and *2way* CfDs because their reference price is based on average instead of power plants' individual market values. Since payments for the *1way* CfD only become relevant, if $v_n \leq S_{i,n}^{1way}$, $S_{i,n}^{2way} = S_{i,n}^{1way} \equiv S_{i,n}^{way}$ are given by:

$$D \cdot \Pi_{i,n} = D \cdot \sum_{t=1}^T \left(q_{t,i,n} p_{t,n} + q_{t,i,n} (S_{i,n}^{way} - v_n) \right) - D \cdot C_{i,n} = 0 \quad (9)$$

$$\Leftrightarrow S_{i,n}^{way} = \frac{C_{i,n}}{\sum_{t=1}^T q_{t,i,n}} + v_n - \frac{\sum_{t=1}^T q_{t,i,n} p_{t,n}}{\sum_{t=1}^T q_{t,i,n}} = l_{coe_{i,n}} + v_n - v_{i,n} \quad (10)$$

with power plant i, n 's individual market value defined as

$$v_{i,n} = \frac{\sum_{t=1}^T q_{t,i,n} p_{t,n}}{\sum_{t=1}^T q_{t,i,n}}. \quad (11)$$

Equation (10) implies that investors expecting their wind power plant's market performance to be above average are able to accept a strike price lower than their expected costs and vice versa. Similarly, the *financial* CfD allows investors to keep their market revenues above those of the reference power plant. Correspondingly, they bid $S_{i,n}^{fin}$, such that it covers lifetime costs plus positive or negative expected net payments, defined by the difference of reference revenues and own market revenues by installed capacity $Q_{i,n}$. Assuming $Q_{i,n}$ to be strictly positive, $S_{i,n}^{fin}$ is given by:

$$D \cdot \Pi_{i,n} = D \cdot \sum_{t=1}^T (q_{t,i,n} p_{t,n}) + D \cdot \left(Q_{i,n} (S_{i,n}^{fin} - r_n) - C_{i,n} \right) = 0 \quad (12)$$

$$\Leftrightarrow S_{i,n}^{fin} = \frac{C_{i,n}}{Q_{i,n}} + r_n - \frac{\sum_{t=1}^T q_{t,i,n} p_{t,n}}{Q_{i,n}} = \frac{C_{i,n}}{Q_{i,n}} + r_n - r_{i,n} \quad (13)$$

with power plant i, n 's market revenues by installed capacity defined as

$$r_{i,n} = \frac{\sum_{t=1}^T q_{t,i,n} p_{t,n}}{Q_{i,n}}. \quad (14)$$

Therefore, in theory, the *1way*, *2way* and *financial* CfD lead to more efficient investment decisions from a system perspective than the *basic* CfD. However, once the power plants are built, they differ in terms of their implications

for dispatch decisions. While *basic* CfDs set the incentive to maximize power generation, regardless of current market prices – also referred to as ‘produce and forget’ strategy –, power plants under a *1way*, *2way* or *financial* CfD would not sell electricity for market prices below their short-term variable costs. Technically, these are defined by operation and maintenance costs. For the *1way* and *2way* CfD, they also depend on expected payments per electricity sold. Power plant operators anticipate to pay or receive the difference between their own market value, $v_{i,n}$ and the reference price, v_n given by the bidding zone’s average wind market value. These anticipated payments at the level of $v_{i,n} - v_n$ per volume of electricity sold constitute so-called *virtual* variable costs or revenues, which lead to dispatch distortions: Wind power plant operators subject to a CfD who expect a to make a payment above the market price in a given hour, incur negative marginal revenues of electricity sales, such that it is rational to curtail wind output. Conversely, wind power is dispatched up to negative market prices at the level of expected positive payments. Hence, only under the *financial* CfD it is optimal to produce if the market price is above or equal to actual technical short-term variable costs. Therefore, in theory, only the *financial* CfD leads to the optimal solution in terms of both the investment decision within the auction phase and the dispatch decision in the operating phase (Schlecht et al., 2024). Yet, this only holds true under the assumption of perfect foresight. In practice, market prices and realized electricity generation are subject to high uncertainty. Typically, investors would reflect those risks by means of a risk premium on the strike price (Fais et al., 2014).

3. Methodology

We evaluate these four different types of CfDs in a fully decarbonised sector-coupled European electricity market. Firstly, we optimise investment and dispatch in a *target* scenario for the future European power system. It reflects the cost-minimal system achieving a certain target share of non-thermal renewables covering European annual electricity demand (Section 3.1). Secondly, we introduce payments of CfDs to the model that are issued by bidding zone to all new wind onshore capacities within a competitive auction (Section 3.2).

3.1. Target Scenario and Data

For our *target* scenario we optimise investment and dispatch in a sector-coupled European power system in absence of CO₂-emitting technologies in an energy system model. It covers all EU27-countries with the exception of Malta but including Great Britain, Norway and Switzerland. We simulate one bidding zone per country or aggregates of countries, i.e., Luxembourg and Germany, the Baltics (covering Lithuania, Latvia and Estonia) and Balkans (covering Hungary, Romania, Bulgaria, Slovakia, Slovenia, Greece, Cyprus and Croatia) (cf. Figure 1b). In the following, we use the terms ‘bidding zone’ and ‘countries’ interchangeably. We follow a brownfield approach considering exogenous generation capacities based on 2030 national estimates for carbon-free technologies, namely, biofuel, waste, nuclear, onshore

wind, offshore wind, solar photovoltaics (PV), centralized solar power (CSP), run-of-river (ROR) hydro, reservoir hydro, pumped hydro, and batteries (ENTSO-E, 2022a). All fossil power plants are assumed to be decommissioned. We allow for endogenous investments in additional carbon-free capacities to meet 2050 projections of electricity and industrial hydrogen (H₂) demand from ENTSO-E (2022b). We use cost 2050 projections (Danish Energy Agency, 2023) and limit investments according to natural potentials (Ruiz et al., 2019). H₂ demand can either be covered by endogenously built electrolysers and H₂ storage or hydrogen imports for 45.07€/MWh (ENTSO-E, 2022b). H₂ can also be used by endogenous combined-cycle gas turbine power plants to generate electricity. We model load shifting from flexible electric vehicles using (TNO, 2023), load shedding by industrial electricity demand according to cost and capacity data from (Gils, 2014). Further load shedding occurs at a maximum price of 4000€/MWh. Bidding zones are connected by exogenous power and hydrogen (H₂) transmission capacities (cf. Figure 1a) (ENTSO-E, 2022b; ENTSO-G, 2023). All of our time-series reflect the weather year 2019. Capacity factor time series of ROR, solar PV, CSP, wind offshore and existing wind onshore as well as reservoir hydro inflows follow one country-specific profile from Pfenninger and Staffell (2016) or Hörsch et al. (2018). For investments in new onshore wind power plants, we define two types of wind power plants per node that differ in terms of their capacity factor time series. Such a difference can relate to either location or technology choice, which was shown to be influenced by support schemes (Schmidt et al., 2013; Grothe and Müsgens, 2013; May, 2017; Meus et al., 2021). We iteratively selected two profiles denoted *profile 1* and *profile 2* per bidding zone from NUTS2-level data with *profile 1* characterized by higher full load hours, but a lower market value than *profile 2* (Pfenninger and Staffell, 2016). Cost and WACC assumptions are uniform for all new wind power plants considered. Therefore, *profile 1* incurs lower LCOE than *profile 2*, but *profile 2*'s higher market value indicates it to be more system-friendly. By means of a constraint, we enforce a minimum share of 95% non-thermal renewables, namely all electricity generation technologies with the exception of biofuel, waste, nuclear and H₂ turbines. As a comparison, we also simulate the same scenario without this constraint and denote it *unconstrained scenario*²

The analysis was carried out using the Backbone energy system modelling and optimisation tool³ (Helistö et al., 2019) integrated in the workflow and scenario manager Spine Toolbox⁴ (Kiviluoma et al., 2022). We employ a soft-linking methodology of an investment optimisation followed by an operational optimisation, both implemented in Backbone in linear programming mode. The investment optimisation phase represents one year using five typical and three extreme weeks. Typical weeks were selected using the k-medoids sampling tool provided by Hoffmann et al. (2022), while extreme weeks were determined iteratively based on load shedding events. The operational optimisation phase employs a rolling horizon approach that sequentially optimises 24 hours in hourly resolution, while modelling the

²The complete dataset is available in a public repository. Since it includes identifying information of the authors of this paper, we will provide a link at revision stage due to the double anonymised review process.

³Backbone public repository: <https://gitlab.vtt.fi/backbone/backbone/>

⁴Spine Toolbox public repository: <https://github.com/spine-tools/Spine-Toolbox> The specific workflow and code used for this project is available in a dedicated public repository. Since it includes identifying information of the authors of this paper, we will provide a link at revision stage due to the double anonymised review process.

remaining 364 days at an increasingly coarser resolution in the forward-looking window (cf. Figure 2 and Helistö et al. (2023)). Under the assumption of perfect competition, we interpret the dual variables of the energy balance constraint resulting from the operational optimisation as wholesale market prices.

Figure 1: Representation of technologies and their structure in our energy system model (a) and its geographical scope with bidding zones represented by one dot connected by transmission grids (b)

3.2. Implementation of CfDs

Within the same model, we simulate four CfD scenarios, each representing one type of CfD as described in section 2. We assume the government to issue CfDs for a target capacity of new wind onshore power plants per bidding zone within a pay-as-bid auction for the strike price of the CfD. Auction participants expect market outcomes according to the *target* scenario. We determine all wind power plants' strike prices by type of CfD according to Equations (8), (10) and (13) using power-plant-specific LCOE and market values as well as reference prices by node and type of CfD resulting from our *target* scenario simulation as denoted by superscript *. To account for the uncertainty of market outcomes, we add a risk premium ρ to the strike price. Risk premia are influenced by a variety of factors, namely, the volume and price risk corresponding to each type of CfD and wind profile, the investors' risk preferences and country-specific financial conditions (Breitschopf and Alexander-Haw, 2022; Đukan and Kitzing, 2023). Since the focus of this paper is the difference in the definition of CfD payments and for simplicity, we assume a uniform risk premium at the level of the WACC, i.e., $\rho = 1.07$, for all wind power plants. As a result, expected annual net payments

for a wind onshore power plant of technology $i \in \{\text{profile 1, profile 2}\}$ in n by type of CfDs are given by:

$$\text{Basic CfD: } \sum_{t=1}^T q_{t,i,n}^* (S_{i,n}^{\text{basic}} \rho - p_{t,n}^*) = \sum_{t=1}^T q_{t,i,n}^* (\text{lcoe}_{i,n}^* \rho - p_{t,n}^*)$$

$$\text{2way CfD: } \sum_{t=1}^T q_{t,i,n}^* (S_{i,n}^{\text{way}} \rho - v_n) = \sum_{t=1}^T q_{t,i,n}^* (\text{lcoe}_{i,n}^* + v_n^* - v_{i,n}^*) \rho - v_n^*$$

$$\text{1way CfD: } \sum_{t=1}^T q_{t,i,n}^* \max \{S_{i,n}^{\text{way}} \rho - v_n^*, 0\} = \sum_{t=1}^T q_{t,i,n}^* \left(\max \{\text{lcoe}_{i,n}^* + v_n^* - v_{i,n}^*, 0\} \rho - v_n^* \right)$$

$$\text{Financial CfD: } Q_{i,n}^* (S_{i,n}^{\text{fin}} \rho - r_n^*) = Q_{i,n}^* \left(\left(\frac{C_{t,i,n}}{Q_{i,n}^*} + r_n^* - r_{i,n}^* \right) \rho - r_n^* \right)$$

Similar to Fais et al. (2014), who express renewable subsidies as a negative cost factor in their bottom up energy system model, we implement CfDs by manipulating wind power plants' costs according to expected CfD payments. For our *1way* and *2way* CfD scenarios, we deduct (add if negative) the expected volume-based net payments, $(S_{i,n}^{\text{way}} \rho - v_n^*)$ and $\max \{S_{i,n}^{\text{way}} \rho - v_n^*, 0\}$, respectively, from technical variable costs of wind onshore (1.22€/MWh). Consequently, our model represents expected virtual variable costs or revenues as described in Section 2. For our *financial* and *basic* CfD scenarios, we manipulate investment costs according to their expected net payments per capacity installed. Particularly, we normalize expected annual payments by installed capacity and lifetime and deduct (or add if neagtive) them from investment costs (960,000€/MW), namely $\frac{1}{A} \frac{1}{A} \sum_{t=1}^T q_{t,i,n}^* (\text{lcoe}_{i,n}^* \rho - p_{t,n}^*)$ for the *basic* CfD and $\frac{1}{A} \left(\left(\frac{c_{t,i,n}^* + AM Q_{i,n}^*}{Q_{i,n}^*} + r_n^* - r_{i,n}^* \right) \rho - r_n^* \right)$ for the *financial* CfD scenario. For the *basic* CfD we additionally set variable costs to our minimum price of 0 to simulate the 'produce and forget' strategy described in Section 2. The capacity target of the auction is represented by limiting the sum of new wind onshore capacities in each bidding zone to *target* scenario results. The zonal distribution between *profile 1* and *profile 2*, however, is optimised in each CfD scenario with the exception of the *basic CfD*: To simulate that within an auction for a *basic* CfD all available capacities of *profile 1* would participate in the auction and would be awarded first, we restrict investment possibilities to this profile, if its natural wind onshore resource limit was not reached in the *target* scenario. Since we assume that all new wind onshore capacities must participate in the auction, we also disable investments in wind onshore profiles that were not built in the *target* scenario. To focus on effects on the two wind onshore profiles, we assume solar and wind offshore capacities to be achieved by an optimal policy instrument ($Q_{\text{solar},n}^{\text{CfD}}$ and $Q_{\text{offshore},n}^{\text{CfD}}$) and fix them at *target* scenario levels. Tables 1 and 2 provide an overview of those assumptions that vary over our scenarios.

4. Results

In this section, we firstly characterize the results of our *target* scenario with an emphasis on the profitability of investments in new wind onshore power plants. Based on its outcomes, we calculate optimal strike prices and ex ante

⁵With the exception of the *basic* CfD scenario, where we only allow investments in *profile 1*, if its natural wind onshore resource limits were not reached in the *target* scenario. Furthermore, we disable profiles that were not built in the *target* scenario.

Table 1

Overview of cost assumptions for new wind onshore by scenario

Scenario	Variable Costs (€/MWh)	Investment Costs (€/MW)
Target	$c=1.22$	$M=960,000$
Unconstrained	$c=1.22$	$M=960,000$
Basic CfD	0	$M - \frac{1}{Q_{i,n}^*} \frac{1}{A} \sum_{t=1}^T q_{t,i,n} (\text{lcoe}_{i,n}^* \rho - p_{t,n})$
1way CfD	$c - \max\{0, (\text{lcoe}_{i,n}^* + v_n^* - v_{i,n}^*) \rho - v_n^*\}$	M
2way CfD	$c - ((\text{lcoe}_{i,n}^* + v_n^* - v_{i,n}^*) \rho - v_n^*)$	M
Financial CfD	c	$M - \frac{1}{A} \left(\left(\frac{c q_{i,n}^* + A M Q_{i,n}^*}{Q_{i,n}^*} + r_n^* - r_{i,n}^* \right) \rho - r_n^* \right)$

Table 2

Overview of other varying assumptions by scenario

Scenario	Maximum capacities new wind onshore	Maximum capacities new solar	Maximum capacities new wind offshore	Share of non-thermal renewables
Target	Natural Potentials	Natural Potentials	Natural Potentials	$\geq 95\%$
Unconstrained	Natural Potentials	Natural Potentials	Natural Potentials	free
All CfDs ⁵	$Q_{\text{profile } i,n}^{\text{CfD}} = \sum_{i=1}^2 Q_{\text{profile } i,n}^*$	$Q_{\text{solar},n}^{\text{CfD}} = Q_{\text{solar},n}^*$	$Q_{\text{offshore},n}^{\text{CfD}} = Q_{\text{offshore},n}^*$	free

Figure 2: Modelling workflow for the target and CfD scenarios

expected cost recovery used for our CfD scenarios (Section 4.1). Subsequently, we compare ex post results of our CfD scenarios to our *target* and an *unconstrained* scenario. Particularly, we contrast the scenarios in terms of invested capacities, share of electricity generation by technology and resulting wholesale electricity prices. Finally, we examine resulting ex post cost recovery under the four types of CfDs from an investor perspective and total system costs from the viewpoint of consumers (Section 4.2).

4.1. Target scenario results: ex ante market expectations

Our *target* scenario results characterize a European energy system dominated by solar PV and wind power capacities followed by battery storage and small amounts of thermal power capacities (cf. Figure 4a). Figure 3 depicts resulting LCOE and market values of new wind power plants' by profile and country. Average market values of new wind power by bidding zone (v_n) are marked by blue asterisks. They lie below time-averaged market prices as marked by red asterisks in almost all bidding zones except for Italy (IT) and Austria (AT). We observe that wind power plants are not profitable in the majority of countries in our *target* scenario with the exception of the Balkans (BK), Germany (DE) and Italy. In theory, market revenues generated by new electricity generation capacities should match their total costs over lifetime when the dual variable of the electricity balance constraint in a linear, perfect foresight cost minimization problem is applied as electricity price (Brown and Reichenberg, 2021). There are several reasons, why our results for wind onshore investments deviate from this theory. Firstly, in Germany, wind onshore *profile 2* it reaches its capacity potential. As shown by Junge et al. (2022), this results in annual market revenues to exceed costs. Secondly, a share of investments in wind power is not solely driven by the cost-minimization, but mandated by the constraint on non-thermal renewable electricity generation as, for instance, in Finke et al. (2023). Thirdly, our soft-coupling approach with an investment run followed by a dispatch run, inherently introduces certain frictions: on the one hand, our dual variables do not include investment costs, such that our method reflects a short- rather than a long-run equilibrium in an electricity market under perfect competition. On the other hand, we simulate investment based on samples of representative weeks, while our scheduling run covers the whole year with a rolling horizon. In that sense, our approach does not assume complete perfect foresight. We argue that this more realistically reflects behavior of market actors who take decisions based on imperfect weather forecasts. Finally, our model represents a brownfield energy system with a significant amount of exogenously installed capacities. We perform several sensitivity analyses suggesting all of these factors to contribute to the finding of non-profitable investments.

Further sensitivity analyses underline the uncertainty of the future electricity market: When applying different representative weeks for our investment simulation, which would translate into different weather forecasts from the perspective of an investor, we find different LCOE and market values in several countries. For instance, wind power becomes profitable in Poland (PL) and Finland (FI), while it becomes unprofitable in Germany (DE) for one different set of representative weeks. An alternative target scenario with a substantially higher price for imported H₂ of 116.9€/MWh according to Brändle et al. (2021) results in profitable wind onshore capacities in the majority of our bidding zones with the exception of Portugal (PT), Spain (ES), France (FR), Sweden (SE), Denmark (DK) and the Baltics (BT) (cf. Figure B.1). These uncertainties of market outcomes illustrate the market risk for investors and constitute a major motive for renewable support schemes in general and CfDs in particular (Beiter et al., 2023).

Figure 3: Levelized cost of energy (LCOE) and market values of new wind onshore capacities distinguished by profile as well as average market prices and average market values of new wind onshore in all modelled bidding zones

Therefore, we remove the non-thermal renewable electricity generation constraint from our support scheme simulations and introduce the four types of CfDs as defined in Section 2. Assuming that investors' market expectations are represented by the *target* scenario results, we calculate strike prices according to Equations (8), (10) and (13) for two wind profiles in each bidding zone. Figure 4 decomposes resulting strike prices in €/MWh for the *basic*, *1way* and *2way* CfDs and in €/MW for the *financial* CfD at the example of France (FR) and Poland (PL). While for the *basic* CfD, strike prices are given by the wind power plant's LCOE plus the risk premium, strike prices additionally include either a markdown or markup for *1way*, *2way* and *financial* CfDs that reflect wind power profile's average market performance. By construction, *profile 2*'s market value is higher than the average market value of each node, such that markups and markdowns for the *1way* and *2way* CfD decrease strike prices for *profile 2* relative to *profile 1*. Compared to the *basic* CfD case this implies an increase in *profile 2*'s, namely the more system-friendly profile's, chances to be awarded a CfD. Conversely, country-wise differences in strike prices between the two profiles for the *financial* CfD do not follow a clear pattern because this CfD pays by capacity, not energy. Analogously to LCOE, costs per capacity are higher for *profile 2* in Poland. In contrast to the *1way* and *2way* CfD, the strike price for this type of wind power plant contains a markup on costs. This results from the fact that a higher market value per energy does not necessarily imply higher market revenues per capacity. In France, the markup is analogous to the *1way* and *2way* CfD, but costs per capacity of *profile 1* are higher than *profile 2*'s. This illustrates that lower LCOE do not necessarily imply lower costs per capacity, when variable costs are larger than zero. Therefore, under the *financial* CfD, it is less

straightforward, which of the two profiles has an advantage in a competitive auction than under the *1way* and *2way* CfD.

Figure 4: Sum of exogenous and endogenous electricity generation and electrolyser capacities in the *target* scenario, 'Wind Onshore' denotes existing and 'Profile 1' and 'Profile 2' new wind onshore capacities (a). Decomposition of optimal strike prices for new wind onshore in France (FR) and Poland (PL) by type of CfD and wind profile calculated based on the *target* scenario results, Basic, 1way and 2way CfD refer to the left y-axis and Financial CfD refers to the right y-axis (b)

Figure 5 displays the proportion of market revenues and net CfD payments of total costs for new wind onshore capacities in Germany, France, Italy, and Poland by profile. We interpret these as investor expectations on cost recovery at the time of the auction. By construction, all investors expect total annual expenses of investing in wind power to be fully covered by the combination of market revenues and CfD payments. An additional markup results from the inclusion of a risk premium in the strike price. However, it is evident that the impact of CfD payments on cost recovery varies across countries: for instance, both types of wind power plants in France rely on governmental subsidy payments to cover around 50% of their expenses, while in Poland, expected subsidy coverage is less than 10%. In Italy, only *profile 2* expects to receive payments from the government, whereas *profile 1* is anticipated to make payments. In Germany wind power is expected to transfer approximately 5-10% of their market revenues to the government. Together with both profiles in the Balkans, these are the only wind power plants that expect to make a payment to the government under our scenario assumptions.

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Figure 5: Ex ante expectations on cost recovery from market revenues and CfD payments of each type according to target scenario results for four selected bidding zones

4.2. CfD scenario results: ex post outcomes

Figure 6 displays investments in wind power capacities, electrolysers, batteries and H₂ turbines across Europe in six simulations: the *target*, *unconstrained* and four CfD scenarios. Solar, wind offshore, and hydro capacities remain constant in all six scenarios by assumption, whereas biofuel, waste, and nuclear power plant capacities do not change by result. In all CfD scenarios, we find new wind onshore capacities to fall below *target* scenario levels. Particularly, zonal wind capacity targets are failed to be met in Germany, the Balkans and Italy. In these three countries wind onshore power plants expected to make payments to the government under the *basic*, *2way* and *financial* CfD. Since CfDs are issued by bidding zone, this reduction in wind investments cannot be balanced by investments in other countries. Aggregated over Europe, at least 90% of the *target* scenario's new wind onshore capacities are reached in all CfD scenarios with the *1way* CfD reaching 97%. With the exception of the *basic* CfD, total wind onshore capacities exceed those of the *unconstrained* scenario. Lower wind capacities are mainly substituted by new H₂ turbine capacities and higher dispatch of other existing thermal capacities. By construction, the type of CfD affects the division of wind capacities between *profile 1* and *profile 2*. The share of *profile 2*, namely the more system-friendly profile with a higher market value, increases in all CfD scenarios except the *basic* CfD. Investments in both electrolyser and battery capacities also increase in all CfD scenarios leading to a rise in electricity demand.

The shares of non-thermal electricity generation of annual demand in the CfD scenarios hardly exceed the *unconstrained* scenario's with the *1way* CfD coming closest to the *target* scenario share (cf. Figure 7). Investment and dispatch incentives set by the different types of CfDs appear to affect the composition of non-thermal electricity generation. In all scenarios, we use the same capacity factor time series of existing wind onshore and the two new wind onshore profiles by bidding zone. However, Figures 8a and 8b show that their full load hours increase in all

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Figure 6: Aggregated investments in new wind onshore, battery, electrolyser and H₂ turbine capacities by scenario

Figure 7: Resulting shares of electricity generation by technology of annual European electricity demand in each scenario, 'Other non-thermal renewables' cover industrial demand response, solar CSP, run of river and pumped hydro storage, while 'Thermal renewables' cover H₂ turbines, biofuel, nuclear and waste power plants, 'Wind Onshore' denotes exogenously installed and 'Wind Onshore Profile 1' and 'Profile 2' endogenously invested wind onshore power plants

CfD scenarios because curtailment is reduced. There are several reasons for this result: Firstly, variable costs were decreased below actual operating costs under the *basic*, *1way* and *2way* CfD scenarios for the majority of new wind onshore capacities. Therefore, they are dispatched at lower prices. Partially, this reduction in curtailment occurs at the

expense of solar PV dispatch, although aggregated vRE curtailment is lower in the CfD scenarios. This relies on a second effect resulting from the variable costs reduction: *Ceteris paribus*, market prices decrease in those hours where new wind power plants are price-setting. Figure 9 depicts price duration curves over all scenarios at the example of Poland (PL). The minimum price equals 0 in the *basic* and reflects negative virtual variable costs in the *1way* and *2way* CfD scenario, respectively. Under the *financial* CfD, it equals technical variable costs of 1.22€/MWh. Notably, the *2way* CfD raises the minimum electricity price in the Balkans because CfD payments induce positive virtual variable costs in this country (cf. Figure A.1). Consequently, wind onshore curtailment increases in the Balkans in this scenario. This effect becomes more prevalent, when we conduct a sensitivity analysis with an alternative target scenario with a higher H₂ price. Since more wind power plants are profitable in this scenario, more wind power plants are required to make payments to the government under the *2way* CfD. Aggregated over Europe, total wind full load hours still increase under this alternative *2way* CfD scenario: While *profile 1*'s full load hours decrease, those of *profile 2*'s and existing wind onshore increase (cf. Figure B.2). This finding suggests a third reason for the reduction in curtailment: As implied by its higher market value, *profile 2* better aligns with system needs than *profile 1*. Therefore, the decrease in *profile 1* capacities under all CfDs except for the *basic* CfD, further reduces curtailment. Consequently, full load hours also increase under the *financial* CfD, although it does not directly affect dispatch via variable costs alterations.

Previous work showed wind onshore and electrolyser deployment to be correlated (Mutke et al., 2023). Hence, the increase in wind full load hours causes an increase in electrolyser investments and activity (Figure 6). Electrolysers have been shown to play a significant role for future electricity market prices (Ruhnau, 2022; Mallapragada et al., 2023). Therefore, the rise in electrolyser activity across all CfD scenarios leads to an increase in the number of hours when they are setting the price. Across Europe, they cause a price plateau at 31€/MWh, which corresponds to opportunity costs of H₂ production (its import price of 45.07€/MWh times electrolyser efficiency 70.5%). Since it can be observed in more hours in the CfD scenarios, the average country-weighted wholesale electricity price in Europe increases from 39.31€/MWh in the *target* scenario to between 42.49€/MWh and 45.15€/MWh (cf. Figure A.1). As we only observe negative market prices in Denmark and Poland under the *1way* and *2way* CfD, they also appear to stabilize market price decreases resulting from variable cost alterations.

Due to these changes in electricity prices, the ex post realized rates of cost recovery from market revenues and CfD payments differ from ex ante expectations, which were formed based on *target* scenario outcomes. As in Ruhnau (2022), electrolysers cause an increase in wind market values resulting in higher rates of cost recovery for almost all wind power plants under all types of CfDs (cf. grey bars in Figure 10). Therefore, in contrast to Frey et al. (2020), volume-based payments under the *1way* and *2way* CfD do not exacerbate the cannibalization effect of wind onshore in our model. Figure 10 also shows that CfD payments increase the likelihood of achieving the desired rate of cost

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Figure 8: Aggregated curtailment relative to total potential generation of wind onshore and solar PV (a) and average wind onshore full load hours (b) by scenario across Europe. ‘Wind Onshore’ denotes exogenously installed and ‘Wind Onshore Profile 1’ and ‘Profile 2’ endogenously invested wind onshore capacities

Figure 9: Price duration curves as the ordered dual variable of the electricity balancing constraint by scenario in Poland

recovery of 107% (100% plus the risk premium), but do not guarantee it. Particularly, *profile 2* does not recover its costs in Spain under the *financial* CfD. In this scenario, the difference in *profile 2*'s and *profile 1*'s market values decreases compared to the *target* scenario. Since the latter values were used to calculate the strike price, the markdown for *profile 2* was overestimated, such that CfD payments do not suffice to recover the power plant's costs. Similar dynamics occur in the *financial* CfD scenario for *profile 2* in the Netherlands, Poland, Germany and Denmark as well as *profile 1* in the Balkans (cf. Figure A.2 and A.3 in the Appendix). In the other CfD scenarios, costs are always recovered ex post with the exception of Germany and the Balkans under the *2way* scenario. Notably, a number of wind power plants in

several countries and scenarios achieve a rate of cost recovery that is significantly higher than 107% (e.g. in France and Italy), while in Germany, for instance, anticipated CfD payments eliminate wind investments in *profile 1*. In general, achieving the ex ante expected rate of cost recovery at the level of 107% seems to be most likely under the *basic* CfD, which is independent of market outcomes. However, even in this scenario, changes to ex ante expectations can occur due to differences in curtailment. These results rely on the assumption that market actors form expectations based on the *target* scenario. However, investors could also anticipate changes in dispatch and market prices induced by the CfDs. To account for this possibility, we conduct two further iterations of the CfD simulations with strike prices calculated based on the results of each respective previous CfD simulation. The results show that across Europe, the rate of ex post cost recovery of wind power most reliably reaches the ex ante expected rate of 107% for the *basic* CfD, whereas it diverges for all countries from the first to the third iteration in the *financial* CfD scenario. In the *1way* and *2way* CfD scenarios, it diverges in the majority of bidding zones. However, it is stable at around 107% in Ireland, Great Britain, Sweden and Belgium, while it appears to converge to this value in Denmark and France. Finally, an update of expected payments leads to the elimination of investments in one or both profiles for some of the CfD scenarios (Balkans, Germany, Italy, Norway, Baltics, Austria and Spain). In sum, we conclude that convergence seems to be unlikely because of the complexity of overall European system effects of the CfDs. Figures 10 and 11 illustrate some of the mentioned examples. Results of the first iteration for all bidding zones are depicted in Figures A.2 and A.3.

Figure 10: Ex post cost recovery of two wind onshore profiles in selected bidding zones in the target scenario and after first CfD iterations decomposed by cost recovery from market revenues and payments to (marked red) or from (marked blue) the government

Figure 11: Ex post cost recovery of two wind onshore profiles in selected bidding zones in the target scenario and after third CfD iterations decomposed by cost recovery from market revenues and payments to (marked red) or from (marked blue) the government

Besides their ability to decrease market price risks for investors, CfDs bear the potential to lower consumer costs. Figure 12 depicts total investment and operating costs of our energy system, costs of importing H₂ and net expenditures under each type of CfD. The latter are compared to what we call *profitability gap* of wind power. It denotes the difference in market revenues and lifetime costs of the unprofitable wind power plants in our *target* scenario. Similar to Roach and Meeus (2020), we argue that this gap has to be paid by some type of subsidy to reach the capacities in the scenario. Therefore, all depicted costs represent the cost burden to be carried by consumers either directly in their electricity bill or indirectly through taxes ignoring costs of other unprofitable technologies. While differences in total costs are relatively small among the scenarios, total costs are lowest in the *financial* CfD scenario, which incurs 272.4 billion € compared to 274.6 billion € in the *target* scenario. Relative to total end consumer electricity and hydrogen demand this difference amounts to 30 ct/MWh. However, due to the increase in domestic H₂ production of hydrogen by electrolyzers, this decrease in system costs comes at the expense of higher wholesale electricity prices. Therefore, hydrogen consumers are more likely to benefit from this decrease in system costs, although exact distributional effects depend on end consumer tariff design. The *financial* CfD also incurs relatively low system costs when conducting our CfD simulations based on an alternative *target* scenario with a higher H₂ price, where most wind power plants are profitable (cf. Figure B.3 in the Appendix). In this scenario, governments even generate net revenues under all CfD

scenarios except for the *Iway* CfD. In general, the result of this sensitivity analysis highlights how crucial the level and distribution of welfare between consumers and generators of electricity will depend on the future price of hydrogen.

Figure 12: System costs over the simulation horizon of 8760 hours by scenario decomposed into operating and investment costs, H₂ import costs and CfD expenditures. The profitability gap in the target scenario represents the difference in annualized costs and market revenues of new wind onshore capacities that is targeted by CfD expenditures

4.3. Discussion

Overall, our results show that all considered types of CfDs can effectively lead to the expansion of wind onshore capacities, but fail to meet the *target* scenario values. However, our model is not able to perfectly capture investor decisions. In contrast to May (2017), Schmidt et al. (2013) or Meus et al. (2021), we do not explicitly model the profit maximization problem of investors, but assume the cost-minimum of an optimisation model to reflect their decision in a perfectly competitive market as in Rosnes (2014) or Özdemir et al. (2020). Using ex ante expectations on subsidy payments within this approach causes the following inherent discrepancy: the costs we deduct from investment and/or operating costs in order to represent CfD payments are based on fixed ex ante calculated expectations. Conversely, the investments made in our (near) perfect foresight simulation include an implicit update of expectations of the market outcome, which, in turn, is not reflected in the applied payments. This causes a deviation from actual incentives set by all volume-based CfDs and the *basic* CfD in particular, as we are not able to perfectly model its induced elimination of price signals. Therefore, for this scenario, we require the additional restriction on investments in *profile 2*, which makes this it less comparable to the other scenarios. Furthermore, we model investment decisions at one specific point of time only and neglect investment pathways or decommissioning decisions.

Yet, we would expect a similar distribution of investments in wind power plant profiles and comparable dispatch effects as a result of a model that captures investment decisions under CfDs mode accurately. The merit of our approach is that we are able to study the implications of these effects on the overall energy system: Alike previous work, we find volume-based support schemes to affect market prices and curtailment (Rosnes, 2014; Pahle et al., 2016; Chaves-Avila et al., 2017). Furthermore, we confirm that support schemes that reward above-average market values enhance investments in system-friendly wind power plants (May, 2017; Schmidt et al., 2013; Meus et al., 2021). Beyond that, our approach demonstrates that these effects are relevant from a system perspective. Particularly, we find the resulting increase in wind full load hours to enhance investments in electrolysers, which, in turn, increase market prices and wind market values. However, this effect could be diminished, if we accounted for levies on electricity consumption used to finance CfD expenditures as in Fais et al. (2014). Furthermore, we are likely to underestimate costs associated with dispatch distortions under volume-based CfDs, since unlike Rosnes (2014) our model neglects ramping constraints and start-up costs. In contrast to our assumptions, their inclusion could also cause negative market prices under the *basic* CfD. Our analysis also ignores the impacts of different types of CfDs on market actors' behavior in sequential markets, although this was one additional motive to develop the *financial* CfD. Theoretically, it constitutes the only type of CfD among the four studied types that does not lead to distortions in sequential markets (Schlecht et al., 2024).

Finally, our *ex ante* and *ex post* analyses of cost recovery provide an indication, if optimised investments in our model could coincide with realistic investor behavior. Considering that new wind onshore is unprofitable in most countries in the *target* and *unconstrained* scenario when assuming a low H₂-price, we argue that our CfD scenarios are more likely to be reached, since they explicitly include payments that completely close the gap between costs and market revenues *ex ante* and almost completely *ex post*. Such forecast errors were shown to be particularly relevant for small solar PV power plants by Castro-Rodríguez and Miles-Touya (2023). *Ex post* remaining missing revenues could be addressed by a more carefully chosen risk premium, which should be subject to future research. Therefore, we can conclude that CfDs can successfully incite the expansion of wind onshore capacities.

5. Conclusion

The future electricity wholesale market is subject to several uncertainties. While the predicted dominance of variable renewables puts downward pressure on market prices, energy demand by sectors coupled with the power system has the potential to lift them above renewables' variable costs. Therefore, electricity market prices shift from being driven by fossil fuel and CO₂ prices to relying on costs of renewable commodities, such as hydrogen. Consequently, both sellers and consumers of electricity are exposed to significant price risks. Contracts for Difference (CfDs) can address these risks. They specify payments between the government and generators of renewable electricity

that are defined by the difference of an ex ante agreed-upon strike price and an ex post determined reference market price. Depending on their specific design, CfDs set different incentives for investment and dispatch.

Our analysis shows that variations in CfD design elements result in relevant differences in a future sector-coupled European power system in absence of carbon pricing. First, we confirm that competitive auctions for different types of CfDs set different incentives during the investment phase: CfDs that are designed to eliminate price signals, are awarded to those power plants that exhibit the lowest levelized costs of energy. Conversely, CfDs that decouple payments from individual market revenues, are more likely to be awarded to power plants with a relatively high market performance, which is associated with a higher value for the power system. At the example of wind onshore, our results show that a higher penetration of such system-friendly power plants leads to an increase in utilization of wind capacities, particularly by electrolyzers. While this effect appears to reduce total system costs with subsidy payments included, average wholesale electricity prices increase as electrolyzers become price-setting in a higher number of hours. Therefore, implications for end consumers of electricity and hydrogen depend on end consumer tariff design.

Second, wind utilization is also affected by dispatch distortions induced by CfDs that are paid by energy sold in the electricity market. Particularly, anticipated CfD payments alter variable costs below or above technical operating costs. Consequently, new wind onshore power plants subject to those CfDs are dispatched up to lower or higher price levels, respectively. Additionally, market prices reflect the altered variable costs in hours, when new wind onshore is price-setting. While in our particular scenario, this increases overall wind utilization, sensitivity analyses show that curtailment can increase, if investors anticipate positive volume-based CfD payments. Furthermore, our analysis neglects potential system costs associated with ramping and start-up costs resulting from these dispatch distortions. Among types of CfDs studied, the newly proposed capacity-based *financial* CfD is the only type that includes relative market performance without distorting dispatch. Consequently, under our assumptions, system costs including subsidy expenditures are lowest in this scenario. Therefore, our modelling results support the conceptual discussion of Schlecht et al. (2024) concluding that the *financial* CfD is most beneficial from a system perspective. However, an implementation of this CfD constitutes a shift from rewarding low costs and high market values per energy to capacity. Our analysis shows that these do not necessarily coincide.

Third, our work underlines that ex post resulting payments of CfDs can deviate from ex ante expectations that are used to define the contracts' underlying strike prices. However, we are able to show that payments resulting ex post from all types of CfDs establish cost recovery for almost all unprofitable wind onshore power plants across Europe. Therefore, we argue that, in general, CfDs are an adequate instrument to promote the expansion of wind onshore capacities. Particularly a *basic* CfD, under which renewables receive or pay the hourly difference of market prices and their LCOE, most reliably achieves the desired rate of cost recovery in our scenarios. However, this comes at the costs of the above-described inefficiencies from a system perspective. Conversely, the more efficient *financial* CfD fails to

entirely recover costs for wind investments in several countries, but increases the rate of cost recovery compared to a situation without any subsidies. An adequate risk premium on the strike price could address this revenue uncertainty and should be subject to future research. Overall, we conclude that our analysis supports the relevance of the conceptual superiority of the *financial* CfD. Constituting a CfD with two-sided payments, it complies with the proposed future obligation of designing support schemes as two-sided CfDs.

Declaration of generative AI and AI-assisted technologies in the writing process

During the preparation of this work the authors used QuillbotAI in order to paraphrase. After using this tool/service, the authors reviewed and edited the content as needed and take full responsibility for the content of the publication.

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Appendix

A. Results for all bidding zones

Figure A.1: Price duration curves as the ordered dual variable of the electricity balancing constraint by scenario and bidding zone. Values above 120€/MWh are excluded from the figure.

Figure A.2: Ex post cost recovery of two wind onshore profiles in nine bidding zones in the target scenario and after first CfD iterations decomposed by cost recovery from market revenues and payments to (marked red) or from (marked blue) the government

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Figure A.3: Ex post cost recovery of two wind onshore profiles in other nine bidding zones in the target scenario and after first CfD iterations decomposed by cost recovery from market revenues and payments to (marked red) or from (marked blue) the government

B. Results for alternative target scenario with higher H₂-price

Figure B.1: Levelized cost of energy (LCOE) and market values of new wind onshore capacities distinguished by profile as well as average market prices and average market values of new wind onshore in all modelled bidding zones in an alternative target scenario with an H₂-price of 116.9 €/MWh

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Figure B.2: Average wind onshore full load hours by scenario based on an alternative target scenario with an H₂-price of 116.9 €/MWh

Figure B.3: System costs over the simulation horizon of 8760 hours by scenario based on an alternative target scenario with an H₂-price of 116.9 €/MWh decomposed into operating and investment costs, H₂ import costs and CfD expenditures.